

DATA REPOSITORY

Data Set	Satellite	Spatial Resolution	Temporal Resolution	Website
NO ₂ concentration	Sentinel-5P (TROPOMI)	7×3.5 km ²	Daily	Google Earth Engine cloud
NO ₂ concentration	AURA (OMI)	13×24 km ²	98.8 Minutes	https://disc.gsfc.nasa.gov/datasets/OMI_MINDS_NO2_1.1/summary?keywords=TROPOMI%20NO2
Forest fires	TERRA(MODIS)	1×1 km ²	Daily	https://firms.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/download/
Lightning effects	TRMM (LIS)	0.5°×0.5°	Hourly	https://search.earthdata.nasa.gov/search?fs10=lightning&fsm0=weather%20events&fst0=atmosphere
Wind	ERA5	0.25°×0.25°	Daily	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=form
NBR	LANDSAT - 8	30×30 m ²	Daily	Google earth Engine cloud

CODES

Matlab

a) SPATIAL CORRLATION BETWEEN LIGHTNING AND NO₂ CONCENTRATION

```
load("OMI_NO2_2012_PREMONSOON.mat");
load("TRMM_LIS_FRD_2012_PREMONSOON.mat");
for i = 1:71
    for j = 1:81
        A = squeeze(U(i,j,:));
        B = squeeze(FRD(i,j,:));
        cor(i,j) = corr(A,B);
        if cor(i,j)<0
            cor(i,j) = nan;
        elseif cor(i,j)>=0
            cor1(i,j) = corr(A,B);
        end
    end
end

figure ()
aa=load('India_lr.txt');
contourf (lon, lat, cor, 'LineStyle', 'none')
% pcolor (lon, lat, cor)
% shading interp;
hold on
colormap jet
colorbar;
hold on
plot(aa(:,1), aa(:,2), '-k', 'linewidth', 1)
colormap jet(10)
colorbar
hold on
lim=[65,100,5,40];
fillout(aa(:,1), aa(:,2), lim, 'w');
xlim([65 100])
ylim([5 40])
clim([0 1])
set(gca, 'FontName', 'Helvetica');
set(gca, 'BoxStyle', 'full', 'Layer', 'top');
% set(gca, 'BoxStyle', 'full', 'CLim', [0 15], 'Layer', 'top');
title('SPATIAL CORRELATION NO2 AND LIGHTNING 2001-2021', 'FontSize', 10)
xlabel('LONGITUDE (^oE)', 'fontweight', 'bold', 'FontSize', 10)
ylabel('LATITUDE (^oN)', 'fontweight', 'bold', 'FontSize', 10)
pbaspect([1 1 1]);
```

The same code can be used to perform spatial correlations for all the seasons by

changing the dataset associated mat file of respective season.

b) WIND PLOT FOR PREMONSOON SEASON

```
clear
clc
fu='ERA_HOURLY_2021_PREMONSOON_SINGLE_LEVEL.nc';
ncdisp(fu);
lon = ncread(fu,'longitude');
lon=double(lon);
latt=ncread(fu,'latitude');
latt=double(latt);
ru=double(ncread(fu,'u10'));
rv=double(ncread(fu,'v10'));

time=double(ncread(fu,'time'));
Time=datevec((time/24)+datenum(1900,01,01));

rum=nanmean(ru(:,:,:),3);
ruv=nanmean(rv(:,:,:),3);

[LON,LAT]=meshgrid(min(lon):2:max(lon),min(latt):2:max(latt));

[X,Y,U]=griddata(lon,latt,rum',LON,LAT);
[X,Y,V]=griddata(lon,latt,ruv',LON,LAT);
M = sqrt((rum).^2+(ruv).^2) ; % magnitude

figure()
% subplot(1,2,1)
aa = load('India_lr.txt');
pcolor(lon,latt,M');
shading interp
hold on
    quiver(X,Y,U,V,2,'k');
hold on
plot(aa(:,1),aa(:,2),'-k','linewidth',1);
hold on
lim=[65,99,5,40];
% plot(aa(:,1),aa(:,2),'-k','linewidth',1)
colormap jet
colorbar
hold on
lim=[65,100,5,40];
% fillout(aa(:,1),aa(:,2),lim,'w');
xlim([65 100])
ylim([5 40])
caxis([-3 10])
set(gca, 'FontName', 'Helvetica');
set(gca, 'BoxStyle', 'full', 'Layer', 'top');
% set(gca, 'BoxStyle', 'full', 'CLim', [0 15], 'Layer', 'top');
title('PREMONSOON WIND 2019', 'FontSize', 10)
xlabel('LONGITUDE (^oE)', 'fontweight', 'bold', 'FontSize', 10)
ylabel('LATITUDE (^oN)', 'fontweight', 'bold', 'FontSize', 10)
pbaspect([1 1 1]);
```

The same code can be used to perform Wind plots for all the seasons by changing the dataset associated mat file of respective season.

c) NO₂ PLOT FOR PREMONSOON SEASON

```
clc
clear
path = 'E:\INTERNSHIP\ISRO INTERNSHIP\SEASONAL FILES\NEW\OMI NO2 DATA\PREMONSOON';
% p = 'OMI-Aura_L3-OMI_MINDS_NO2d_2012m0525_v01-00-2020m1028t144425';
% ncdisp(p);
year=2012;
[lat,lon,conc,time] = deal([]);
dir1 = dir(strcat(num2str(year),'\*.nc'));
s = length(dir1);

for k = 1:size(dir1)

        lon =
double(ncread(strcat(dir1(k).folder,'\ ',dir1(k).name),'Longitude'));
        lat =
double(ncread(strcat(dir1(k).folder,'\ ',dir1(k).name),'Latitude'));
        time(k,1) =
double(ncread(strcat(dir1(k).folder,'\ ',dir1(k).name),'Time'));
        conc(:, :,k) =
double(ncread(strcat(dir1(k).folder,'\ ',dir1(k).name),'ColumnAmountNO2TropCloudScreened'));
        value =
double(ncread(strcat(dir1(k).folder,'\ ',dir1(k).name),'ColumnAmountNO2TropCloudScreened'));

end

c = nanmean(conc,3);
Time = datevec((time)+datenum(1972,01,01));

conc1=[];
m=3:5;
for k=1:3
    ind=find(Time(:,2)==m(k));
    conc1(:, :,k)=nanmean(conc(:, :,ind),3);
end

del_s = 0.5;
[LAT,LON]=meshgrid(0:del_s:40,65:del_s:100);

CON =[];

for i=1:3
CON(:, :,i) = conc1(:, :,i);
[X,Y,U(:, :,i)] = griddata(lon,lat,CON(:, :,i)',LON,LAT);
end

[X1,Y1,R]=griddata(lon,lat,c',LON,LAT);

save('OMI_NO2_2012_PREMONSOON.mat','X','Y','c','U')
S=load("OMI_NO2_2012_PREMONSOON.mat");

figure()
```

```

aa=load('India_lr.txt');
% contourf(lon,lat,cor,'LineStyle','none')
pcolor (X1,Y1,R)
shading interp;
hold on
colormap jet
colorbar;
hold on
plot(aa(:,1),aa(:,2),'-k','linewidth',1)
colormap jet
colorbar
hold on
lim=[65,100,5,40];
fillout(aa(:,1),aa(:,2),lim,'w');
xlim([65 100])
ylim([5 40])
clim([0 5*(10^15)])
set(gca, 'FontName', 'Helvetica');
set(gca, 'BoxStyle', 'full', 'Layer', 'top');
% set(gca, 'BoxStyle', 'full', 'CLim', [0 15], 'Layer', 'top');
% title('NO2 CONC FOR PREMONSOON SEASON', 'FontSize', 10)
xlabel('LONGITUDE (^oE)', 'fontWeight', 'bold', 'FontSize', 10)
ylabel('LATITUDE (^oN)', 'fontWeight', 'bold', 'FontSize', 10)
pbaspect([1 1 1]);

```

The same code can be used to perform AURA/OMI NO₂ concentration plots for all the seasons by changing the dataset associated mat file of respective season.

GOOGLE EARTH ENGINE:

NO2 CONC AND FOREST FIRES:

```
var India = ee.FeatureCollection ("users/abheendra98/INDIA_SHAPE_FILE")
Map.addLayer(India, {color: 'white'}, 'Region of Interest');
var collection = ee.ImageCollection('COPERNICUS/S5P/OFFL/L3_NO2')
  .select('tropospheric_NO2_column_number_density')
  .filterDate('2021-10-01', '2021-12-01');
var band_viz = {
  min: 0,
  max: 0.0002,
  palette: ['black', 'blue', 'purple', 'cyan', 'green', 'yellow', 'red']
};
print(India)
Map.addLayer(collection.mean().clip(India), band_viz, 'S5P N02');
Map.centerObject(India, 5);
//FOREST FIRE
var dataset = ee.ImageCollection('FIRMS').filter(
  ee.Filter.date('2021-10-01', '2021-12-01'))
  .filterBounds(India)
  .select(['T21']);
var fires = dataset.select('T21');
var firesVis = {
  min: 325.0,
  max: 400.0,
  palette: ['red', 'orange', 'yellow'],};
Map.addLayer(fires, firesVis, 'Fires');
Map.centerObject(India, 5);
var simple = India.map(function(feature){
  return feature.bounds()})
var India = simple.geometry()
```